

EXTRACTION AND CHARACTERISATION OF CELLULOSE MICROFIBRILS FROM *PONGAMIA PINNATA* SEED SHELL

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ABSTRACT

Biodiesel is a renewable resource of energy and has gained its importance in India due to soaring oil price and largely enhanced environmental awareness. Biodiesel and other biofuels are produced from agricultural plant and plant products. *Pongamia Pinnata* seeds have been identified as a superior and more sustainable source of biodiesel. The process generates large amount of unused *Pongamia Pinnata* seed shell. The present paper reports isolation of cellulose microfibrils from *Pongamia Pinnata* seed shell using chlorination and alkaline extraction process. The morphology of the cellulose microfibrils was investigated by Scanning Electron Microscopy. The cellulose microfibrils had diameter in the range of 0.8-2.6 μm . The crystallinity index obtained from X-ray diffraction and spectrums from Fourier transform infrared and Nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy for seed shell and extracted cellulose microfibrils, showed that the chemical treatments removed most of the hemicellulose and lignin from the seed shell fibers. The thermal stability of the fibers was analysed using thermogravimetric analysis, which demonstrated that thermal stability was enhanced noticeably for cellulose microfibrils. This work provides a new approach for more effective utilisation of *Pongamia Pinnata* seed shell to examine their potential use as reinforcement fibres in biocomposites.

Key words: Cellulose fibers, Chemical treatment, Hemicellulose, Lignin, *Pongamia Pinnata* seed.

1. INTRODUCTION

Cellulose is the most abundant polymer available in nature. Highly-purified cellulose fibers have been isolated from several plant sources, such as wood (1), bamboo (2, 41), cotton (34), soy hulls (4), hemp (35), sisal (22, 25), branch-barks of mulberry (18), pineapple leaf fibres (7, 21), pea hull fibre (6), coconut husk fibers (28), banana rachis (42) sugar beet (9, 10), wheat straw (17), hemp (24, 14), jute (26, 29), palm leaf sheath (20), Oil palm biomass residue (12), *Arundodonax* L stem (11), Cotton stalk (16), Agave (27), and Alfa fibers (32). The application of these cellulose fibers in composite materials has gained increasing attention in the past two decades (15). In view of better utilization of renewable natural resources, there is a need to explore the abundantly available waste material from other industries as greener sources, which can be utilized in developing high strength light weight bio-composites for high-end applications. Thus, *Pongamia pinnata* seed shell, a waste material from biodiesel production plants has been chosen in the present work to exploit its potential for the production of cellulose fibers, which may find their application as reinforcement material in biocomposites.

In India and South East Asia, *Pongamia pinnata* seeds are used as significant fuel source (8). *Pongamia pinnata* is a medicinal plant with all its parts having medicinal uses (40). Biofuel is the most important product of the *P. pinnata* tree in some parts of the world. Hence, large numbers of trees are grown in farms and availability of the seed shell is more (30). Cellulose percentage in the seed shell is approximately 40 % and is similar as in shelly wood (23) and hence these seed shells can find potential application as a source for cellulose fibers. In the present work the cellulose fibers were isolated from the *Pongamia pinnata* seed shell using chlorination and alkaline process. The isolated cellulose microfibrils were characterized using FTIR, NMR, XRD,

SEM and TGA for their morphological, thermal and crystalline properties in order to evaluate their potential as reinforcement in biocomposites.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

The *Pongamia pinnata* seed shells were collected from University of Agricultural Sciences, Bangalore, Karnataka, India. All the chemicals used were of analytical grade.

Fiber processing

The *Pongamia pinnata* seed shells were separated from dust and mud particles by washing them extensively in tap water and finally with distilled water. The seeds were then dried under sunlight for two days and stored in sealed polythene bags for further use. Cleaned seeds were ground into powder (using 60 mesh) and dried at 105⁰C in hot air oven for 8 h.

Preparation of Cellulose microfibrils

Cellulose microfibrils were isolated from *Pongamia pinnata* seed shell by using chlorination and alkaline extraction process (31). *Pongamia pinnata* seed shell fibers were taken in fritted- glass crucible and dried at 105⁰C in hot air oven until weight remained constant to ensure moisture free fiber. The fibers were dewaxed by extraction with toluene-ethanol mixture in 2:1 ratio for 6h taken in a Soxhlet apparatus. Excess of solvent from the fibers was removed by suction and later kept for drying in hot air oven. Fibers were delignified by treating with (7 kg/m³) sodium chlorite solution adjusted to pH 4 - 4.2 by the addition of acetic acid and sodium acetate buffer, at 100⁰C for 2 h with fiber to liquor ratio of 1:50. Filtered fibres were extensively washed with 2 % sodium bisulphate, distilled water and ethanol. The fibers were then treated with (175 g/l) NaOH solution at 20⁰C for 45 min, filtered, washed with 10 % acetic acid and then with distilled water, finally dried at 105⁰C in an oven. The fibers were treated with 8% acetic acid and 7 % nitric acid taken in 15:1 ratio at 120⁰C for 15 minutes. The mixture was then cooled, filtered and washed sequentially with 95 % ethanol and distilled water and finally dried at 105⁰C in an oven until it reached a constant weight.

Characterization

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM)

Scanning electron microscope (JSM-6380LA, Jeol, EVISA), was used to study the morphology of the untreated fibers and extracted cellulose fibers.

Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR)

The FTIR spectra of the untreated and cellulose fibers were recorded using Fourier transform infrared (IR Prestige21 Shimadzu, Japan spectrometer) with the ATR crystal.

X-ray analysis (XRD)

The X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns were obtained with X-ray Diffractometer (X'Pert³ Powder, PANalytical, The Netherlands). The Crystallinity Index (CI) was calculated using the Segal method.

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA)

The thermal stability of untreated fibers and extracted cellulose fibers was established using a thermogravimetric analyser (TGA Q50, TA instruments, USA).

¹³C NMR (CP-MAS) spectroscopy

¹³C CP-MAS NMR spectra of untreated fibers and extracted cellulose microfibrils were run on Bruker DSX 300 MHz solid-state NMR.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Morphological characteristics

In their natural state, and before chemical extraction, fiber surfaces have waxes and other encrusting substances such as hemicellulose, lignin and pectin that form a thick outer layer to protect the cellulose inside. The presence of encrusting substances causes the fibers to have an irregular appearance, as shown in Figure 1 a. During fiber extraction, most of the surface waxes and other noncellulosic substances are removed and the resulting surface is shown in Figure 1 b. It is clear that some cell tissues have been destroyed during the process and the connection between cells are looser than in the case of the untreated fibers. This could be attributed to the preferential degradation of the labile components, such as acid-soluble lignin and hemicellulose (33). The diameter of cellulose fibers varied from 0.8 μm – 2.6 μm .

Figure.1: Scanning electron microscope images a) dewaxed *Pongamia pinnata* seed shell and b) cellulose fibers after chemical extraction.

Alkaline treatment of fibers disrupts the lignin structure and help to separate the structural linkages between lignin and carbohydrates (10, 35-39). Purification by mild alkali treatment results in the solubilization of lignin and remaining pectins and hemicelluloses.

Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR)

The FT-IR spectroscopy monitors the functional groups present in the fibers as shown in Fig 2. The spectra in Figure 2b showed the typical band pattern for cellulose, hemicellulose and lignin moiety. The band 3331 cm^{-1} corresponds to stretching $-\text{OH}$ groups, 2895.51 cm^{-1} corresponds to C-H stretching. The band at 1639.49 cm^{-1} corresponds to absorbed water, 1024 cm^{-1} corresponds to C-O stretching, 1365.60 cm^{-1} corresponds to C-H asymmetric deformation of cellulose. The bands at 1730 and 1509 cm^{-1} attributed to hemicellulose and lignin, respectively. These peaks disappeared in the cellulose fibers as shown in figure 2a, indicating the efficiency of the isolation method which broke the bonds of the hemicellulose and lignin, thereby removing those (13). There is no band at 1736 cm^{-1} because of lignin and hemicellulose removal, which accounts for carbonyl groups $\text{C}=\text{O}$ due to presence of acetyl ester and carbonyl aldehyde groups of hemicellulose and lignin. At 1510 cm^{-1} in the spectrum represent the $-\text{C}=\text{C}-$ stretch of the aromatic rings of lignin, the lack of the peak was attributed to the removal of lignin.

Figure 2: FT-IR spectra of a) purified cellulose fibers and b) untreated fibers of *Pongamia pinnata* seed shell

¹³C NMR (CP-MAS) spectroscopy

The ¹³C NMR spectra of untreated and purified cellulose microfibrils are shown in Figure 3. The spectrum of *Pongamia pinnata* seed shell fibers shows mainly the corresponding signals for the cellulose, hemicellulose and lignin. All noticeable peaks of the cellulose carbon atoms occurred between 60 and 110 ppm. The sharp peaks at 107.69 ppm, 77.5 ppm and 67.4 ppm are due to the ordered cellulose C-1, C-2 and C-6 carbons respectively, while the peaks at 87 ppm and 65 ppm are due to the disordered cellulose C-4 and C-6 carbons, as well as due to the less ordered cellulose chains of the crystallite surfaces. The peaks at 75- 84 ppm correspond to the C-3, C-4, and C-5 carbons of cellulose. The peaks of lignin and especially cellulose overlap the peaks assigned to hemicellulose. The carbohydrate peaks of the hemicellulose should be at 103 ppm (C-1), 84 ppm (C-4), 72-75 ppm (C-2 and C-3) and 65 ppm (C-5), but the strong cellulose peaks overlap these peaks. The methyl and carboxylic carbons of acetyl groups attached to hemicellulose peaks occurred at 23.9 and 174 ppm,

respectively. The peaks between 110 and 170 ppm were assigned to different aromatic carbons of lignin. The wide peak between 110-125, 125-142 and 142-167 ppm correspond C2 and C6; C1 and C4; C3 and C5 aromatic carbons of lignin.

Figure 3: ¹³C NMR spectra of untreated and purified cellulose fibers of *Pongamia pinnata* seed shell

In addition, the peak between 10 and 38 ppm was attributed to the methyl and alkyl carbons (including acetyl groups in hemicellulose), while the peaks at 58 ppm were attributed to methoxyl (-OCH₃) and carbonyl groups respectively in lignin. The extracted cellulose microfibrils spectrum is also shown in Figure 3. It can be seen that the peaks at 110-167 ppm, 56 ppm and 10-35 ppm of lignin, as well as 20.8 and 171 ppm of hemicellulose peaks disappeared, indicating that hemicellulose and lignin were successfully removed as a result of the different chemical treatments by cellulose extraction process. While the other (cellulose) peaks, i.e., those appeared in the region 60-110 ppm almost remained the same (20). These observations are very much in consistent with the FTIR spectral data of cellulose microfibrils of *Pongamia pinnata* seed shell.

Thermal Gravimetric analysis (TGA)

The thermograms presented in Figure 4 of untreated fibers and cellulose fibers of *Pongamia pinnata* seed shell fibers show the degradation temperature of untreated *Pongamia pinnata* seed shell fibers as 200^oC and chemical treated cellulose fibers as 270^oC. TG curves show several decomposition steps. In a nitrogen atmosphere, the main peak appears at around 250 °C and is due to the thermal decomposition for the pyrolysis of cellulose (5, 19). In both the cases, a small weight loss was found in the range of 40-180 °C due to the evaporation of humidity of the materials or the low molecular weight compounds remaining after the isolation procedures.

Figure 4: Thermograms of untreated fiber and cellulose fibers *Pongamia pinnata* seed shell fibers.

The high weight loss at higher temperatures indicate the thermal decomposition of the purified cellulose fibers at high temperatures related to the partial removal of hemicelluloses, lignin, and pectin from the fibers, as well as the higher crystallinity of cellulose (1). Fiber residue remained in both samples upto 450°C, indicating the presence of carbonaceous materials in the shell fibers in the nitrogen atmosphere. The high thermal properties of the microfibrils may broaden the fields of application of cellulose fibers, especially at temperatures higher than 200 °C for biocomposite processing.

X-ray Diffraction (XRD)

Figure 5 shows the equatorial X-ray diffraction patterns and the relative degrees of cellulose crystallinity, respectively. The peaks were observed for both samples at $2\theta = 16^\circ$ and 22.6° . The peak at $2\theta = 16^\circ$ corresponds to the (1 1 0), and crystallographic peaks at $2\theta = 22.6^\circ$ correspond to the (0 0 2). The crystallinity index (IC) of untreated fibers and cellulose fibers was 27.2 % and 47 % respectively. The increase in crystallinity of cellulose fibers after chemical treatment was due to removal of hemicellulose and lignin, which exist in the amorphous region. The crystallinity of the purified cellulose of *Pongamia pinnata* seed shell was increased by 19.8 %. Alkali treatment of the natural fiber leads to the swelling of the fiber and a subsequent increase in the absorption of moisture and leads to the removal of cementing materials like lignin, hemicelluloses, and pectin which will result in the increase of percentage crystallinity of the fiber (28).

Figure 5: X-ray diffraction patterns of *Pongamia pinnata* seed shell untreated fibers and chemically treated cellulose fibers.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, the cellulose isolation from *Pongamia pinnata* seed shell by chlorination and alkaline process was evaluated and the obtained microfibrils were characterized by TGA, FTIR SEM, NMR and XRD analysis. The morphological analysis carried out by SEM confirms that cellulose microfibrils were obtained with diameter 0.8-2.6 μm , while the FTIR and NMR results confirmed the removal of hemicelluloses and lignin. On consideration of the thermal behaviour of the untreated and cellulose fibres the rise of degradation temperature to 70⁰C confirms the removal of hemicelluloses and lignin. Similarly the crystallinity of cellulose fibers increased by 19.8% compared to untreated fibers. Thus this work evidences the success of the applied extraction procedure and the possibility to obtain cellulose microfibrils from *Pongamia pinnata* seed shell which may find potential application as filler to involve in the production of biodegradable composites with enhanced properties.

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